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LASU Journal of Management and Social Sciences is a multi-disciplinary journal published by the Lagos State University, Nigeria. Its major aim is to serve as rallying-point for intellectual brainstorming and to contribute towards the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria by providing a forum for ideas initiated and empirically tested by research experts to be published for the benefit of Policy Makers, Administrators and other functionaries in both the private and public sectors of the Nigerian economy.

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The belief is that an information bank such as this would be beneficial for poverty

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ECONOMIC IMPACT OF COOPERATIVE SOCIETIES ON SMALL SCALE BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT IN ABA, ABIA STATE, NIGERIA

* Victor Monday Dibie

** Ogechi Grace Amadi-Ebere

*** Nwaobiwe Queen Nwanyisunday

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ABSTRACT

The study examined economic impact of cooperative societies on small scale business development in Aba, Abia State, Nigeria. Economic impact of cooperative societies was proxied by access to financial security for the members, cooperative saving habit, storage facility provision and marketing agencies of products, while small scale business development in Aba was maintained as dependent variable. A descriptive research design was used for the study. The population of the study consisted of 545 members of the studied cooperative societies operating small businesses. The sample of the study 202 was drawn through Taro Yamane formula and simple random sampling technique was used. Questionnaire was the major instrument for data collection. Simple linear regression analysis was used to test hypotheses. The result of the findings indicated that, there is significant effect of access to financial security by the members on small scale business development in Aba, Abia State. Also, there is significant effect of cooperative saving habit on small scale business development in Aba. There is significant effect of marketing agencies of products on small scale business development in Aba, Nigeria. However, there is no significant effect of storage facility provision on small scale business development in Aba, Abia State. In conclusion, there is a large economic impact of cooperative societies on the small-scale business development in Aba, Abia State. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommended that since, there is significant effect of access to financial security by the members on small scale business development, cooperative societies should encourage members to have quick accessibility to loans and they should be faithful to repay their overdue loans. Also, the government should provide viable means of assisting cooperative societies to improve their management activities.

Keywords: Cooperative Societies, SMEs, Financial Security, Cooperative Saving Habit, Storage Facility Provision and Marketing Agencies.

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria's economy is dominated by small businesses in agriculture, manufacturing, commerce, industry and services. Small businesses in Nigeria like any other parts of the world are seen as the backbone of all economies and they are key sources of economic growth, development most especially in ravaging many industries (Ohen, Ofem & Arikpo,

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2018). The most ambitious move ever made by the government was the establishment of the Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) in order to facilitating access to credit, technology and market for the SMEs through different agencies like CBN, development banks and cooperative societies (Ogboru, 2017). And the Nigerian cooperatives societies have always played a key role in the promotion and development of small businesses (Ademilua, 2017). Indeed, promotion and support of business enterprise of members and jointly owned businesses are at the core of cooperative functional activities. However, this promotional engagement is often neglected since policy makers often see cooperative societies as simply a channel for poverty alleviation and rural development and relates to them as such. Thus, some entrepreneurs are yet to come to terms with the fact that cooperatives are first and foremost businesses promotion agents whose potential capabilities could be utilized to further promote SMEs (Okoli, 2018).

Cooperative societies can play an important economic role in facilitating access to credit procurement and storage distribution of input and marketing of products and encouraging saving habits. The cooperative creates employment opportunities particularly in the rural areas and allow disadvantaged groups to be organized for social and economic benefit. The cooperative and thrift societies are formed with the idea of cooperation. Every cooperative society is formed to render service to its members rather than to earn profit (Ohen *et al.*, 2018). Generally, it is seen that cooperative societies do not function efficiently due to lack of managerial talent. The gains to the Nigerian economy during the pre-oil era were largely due to positive effects arising from general acceptance by the people of cooperative movements. Unfortunately, those attractions no longer exist today as they have been eroded away with the petroleum becoming the dominant commodity and the mainstay of the economy. Despite these numerous benefits of the cooperative societies, many cooperators seem not to gain or reap substantially from being membership of various cooperative societies in terms of capital formation and the improvement of their welfare status. Cooperative society describes as a business organization in which a group of individuals who have a common interest, mutually agree to join together to form the business in order to promote their economic activities such as production, distribution, or marketing of goods and services, and for the provision of welfare benefits to the members (Brown, 1994 in Effiom, 2017).

The introduction of modern cooperative business into Nigeria dates back to the year 1935 following the acceptance by the colonial administration of Mr. C, F, Strickland's report on the prospects of cooperative in Nigeria (Agbo and Chidebelu, 2020). In his submission, Bello (2015) stated that for over 160 years, cooperatives had been an effective way for people to exert control over their economic livelihoods as they play an increasingly important role in facilitating job creation, economic growth and social development. However, cooperative societies offer communities opportunities to create employment for the residents, generate power in the market place, make goods and services available, prevent the leakage of participants money and assist in youth retention (Gibson, 2015). A cooperative society is a user owned and democratically controlled business from which benefits are derived and distributed equitably based on use or as a business owned and controlled by the people who use its services (United States Department of Agriculture Rural Development, 2022).

More so, Kareem, Arigbabu, Akintaro and Badmus (2022) stated that democracy of cooperative society is an institutional arrangement for arriving at collective decisions, realize the common goals by making the people itself decide issues through the election of the representative that assemble to carry out its will. Cooperatives were observed as having a political as well as an economic objective, and also as a response to the lay-offs of workers and rising unemployment (Develtere, Pollet and Wanyama, 2018). Cooperative is a typical social, economic enterprise organized by the people and run by themselves, naturally they

would ensure that they reaped the benefit of their labour, so, as a grass root organization, it is the people in the cooperative society that should be given the most attention (Othman, Kari, Jani and Hamdan, 2022). Accordingly, The Medium-Term Agricultural Development Strategy (MTADS) remarks that grassroots organizations will be important in the privatization objective, specifically in the marketing of agricultural inputs and products, as well as in providing cohesive groups suitable for extension work and joint borrowing and mobilizing savings. Co-operatives are usually an autonomous association of persons united voluntarily to meet their common economic, social and cultural needs and aspirations through a jointly owned and democratically controlled enterprise (Conn, 2018). The participants observe cooperative society as a way of generating finances for the development of small enterprises. One of the characteristics of a cooperative society is their dual goal: socially, supporting their members and economically, acting as an enterprise in the market.

Despite the economic power of cooperative, the cooperative societies as an informal source of finance have serious setbacks (Okoli, 2018). One of these problems is the inadequate amount of capital that can be raised from the members of the cooperative society when compared to the need of small industrialists. There are factors however that have militated against the efficiency of cooperative sector as an economic tool of microfinance, job creation, poverty eradication and wealth creation. Some of these are bad leadership, lack of mutual training and exposure to modern management techniques, ambiguous government role in the cooperative movement, as well as the challenges of the changing world. The perceived benefits and problems of cooperative societies in the financial sector era is worthy of exploration.

The main objective of the study was to examine the economic impact of cooperative societies on small scale business development in Aba, Abia State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the effect of access to financial security for the members on small scale business development in Aba;
- ii. Determine the effect of cooperative saving habit on small scale business development in Aba;
- iii. Analyze the effect of storage facility provision on small scale business development in Aba; and
- iv. Find out the effect of marketing agencies of products on small scale business development in Aba.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Concept of Cooperative Society

A cooperative is any group of people who have voluntarily agreed to cooperate, i.e., to put their resources together and to work together towards the achievement of a common economic and/or social goal in a joint, financially viable, enterprise (Adekunle and Henson, 2017). A cooperative must be run in a democratic way by its members although its day-to-day management can be vested in the hands of skilled non-member managers, supervised by a democratically elected body of members. In a cooperative each member works, has one share and one vote (Adekunle and Henson, 2017). A cooperative is a private business organization that is owned and controlled by the people who use its products, supplies or services. Although cooperatives vary in types and membership size, all were formed to meet the specific objectives of the members, and are structured to adapt to a member's changing needs.

A cooperative is a collective group of individuals who boost their members' economic wellbeing by creating a democratically controlled business enterprise. Farmers join agricultural cooperatives to address obstacles such as hunger, business loss, missing resources in the manufacturing chain, reduced wages, higher financing costs with trades, and a commitment to productivity expansion (Karli, 2016). Cooperatives have a significant effect on the success of businesses. Cooperatives must increase their productivity to assist their members.

Cooperatives are defined as autonomous associations of persons who unite voluntarily to meet their common economic and social needs and aspirations through a jointly owned and democratically controlled enterprise (FAO, 2016). Cooperatives are established by like-minded persons to pursue mutually beneficial economic interest and they provide a unique tool for achieving one or more economic goals in an increasingly achieving economy of size, improving bargaining power when dealing with other business, purchasing in bulk to achieve lower prices, and obtaining products and services otherwise unviable. Cook (2019) described cooperatives as a medium through which services such as provision of farm inputs, farm implements, farm mechanization, agricultural loans, agricultural extension, members education, marketing of members farm produce, and other economic activities and services are rendered to members. Farmers' cooperatives provide smallholder farmers with economics scale by facilitating cheaper and more efficient access to inputs, production technologies, marketing information, and markets (Gamba and Komo, 2019).

The survival and operations of cooperative societies in any society in a country depend largely on the overall political and economic environment of such nation because cooperatives exist within the wider economy of the particular country where it operates (Calkins and Ngo, 2020). The practice of cooperative has grown over the years across the globe either as formal or informal institutions. The regulation of farmers cooperative is a function of the roles they are expected to perform in any nation's economy, with regard to the level of economic development and poverty in such a nation (Oluyombo, 2020). Cooperative will track records of prudent management and cohesive membership stand to play a major role in agricultural and rural development in Nigeria. The contribution of aquaculture and fisheries to the Nigeria economy is tremendous but not properly managed by the individuals as well as the government. Lack of cooperation contributed to the major problems of aquaculture in Nigeria.

Significance of Cooperative Societies

Cooperative society has an important role to play in the economic system for the efficient development of any industry in Nigeria. It best combines the personal, collective, and public interests. Its role and importance have considerably increased. More people are paying attention to cooperation, seeing in it the possibility of surviving despite the difficult economic situation. Cooperatives have long been recognized to play important roles in society that translate into the improvement of living conditions of their members, particularly the low-income earning cadres of the population; the rural people and the urban poor. Cooperatives aggregate people, resources and capital into economic units. Being voluntary, democratic and self-controlled business organizations, cooperatives offer the institutional framework through which local communities gain control over the productive activities from which they derive their livelihood (Adeyemo and Bamire, 2015). Cooperatives provide the opportunity for farmers in the rural areas to raise their incomes. They are democratic organizations empowering people to find their own solutions. They increase financial security for the members, and contribute directly and indirectly to gender equality (Armando, 2019).

Cooperatives for years had been dedicated to conducting business in a way now acknowledged as the most effective route to transformational development: putting people in-

charge of their own destinies and helping to bring services to their communities; increase decision making trust and accountability through democratic participation; provide a profitable connection to private sector; build and protect assets at the community level; and, limit the role of government and working together to resolve problems (OCDC, 2017). Co-operatives are sometimes the only providers of services in rural communities, given that traditional companies often find it too costly to invest in these areas. Co-operatives improve living conditions, solve specific socio-economic problems which include income generating; support rural development and preserve viability of rural communities. Cooperative societies are formed based on certain principles which distinguished them from other business organizations. Odey (2016) asserts that such principles may be based upon the new models of scientific management of businesses and applied economics.

Contributions of Cooperative Societies to Economic Development

Cooperatives are community-based, rooted in democracy, flexible, and have participatory involvement, which makes them well suited for economic development (Gertler, 2021). The process of developing and sustaining a cooperative involves the processes of developing and promoting community spirit, identity and social organization as cooperatives play an increasingly important role worldwide in poverty reduction, facilitating job creation, economic growth and social development (Gibson, 2015). In a study carried out by Chikaire (2021), outlined numbers of ways, cooperative societies have contributed to the economic, social, and national development of Nigeria. With regard to economic and social development, cooperatives societies promote the “fullest participation of all people” and facilitate a more equitable distribution of the benefits of globalization. They contribute to sustainable human development and have an important role to play in combating social exclusion to economic development. Thus, the promotion of cooperatives society should be considered as one of the pillars of national and international economic and social development (Levin, 2020).

Cooperatives are viewed as important tools for improving the living and working conditions of both women and men. Since, the users of the services they provide owned them, cooperatives make decisions that balance the need for profitability with the welfare of their members and the community, which they serve. As cooperatives foster economies of scope and scale, they increase the bargaining power of their members providing them, among others benefits, higher income and social protection. Hence, cooperatives accord members opportunity, protection and empowerment - essential elements in uplifting them from degradation and poverty (Somavia, 2020). As governments around the world cut services and withdraw from regulating markets, cooperatives are being considered useful mechanisms to manage risk for members and keep markets efficient (Henehan, 2019).

In addition to the direct benefits they provide to members, cooperatives strengthen the communities in which they operate. According to Somavia (2020) cooperatives are specifically seen as significant tools for the creation of decent jobs and for the mobilization of resources for income generation. Many cooperatives provide jobs and pay local taxes because they operate in specific geographical regions. According to Levin (2020) it is estimated that cooperatives employ more than 100 million men and women worldwide. In Nigeria, cooperatives can provide locally needed services, employment, circulate money locally and contribute to a sense of community or social cohesion. They can provide their employees with the opportunities to upgrade their skills through workshops and courses and offer youth in their base communities short and long-term employment positions. Students could also be employed on casual-appointment basis during long vacations. Through these, cooperatives will contribute to economic development (Chikaire, 2021).

Ways Cooperatives Promote SMEs

Cooperatives are known to have assisted in the establishment and development of SMEs through its role in entrepreneurship promotion; raising capital; provision of infrastructural facilities; small scale industrialization; and developing small holder agriculture (Somavia, 2020).

1. **Role in Entrepreneurship Promotion:** Entrepreneurship is seen here as the practice of starting a new business or reviving an existing business, in order to capitalize on new found opportunities. Cooperatives have long been identified and associated with promoting entrepreneurship not only on their jointly owned businesses but also in the individual business units of their members. Cooperatives by their nature and antecedents have always been pro-entrepreneurship. Of the cooperative efforts in this regard, the former United Nations Secretary-General Boutros Boutros-Ghali, in his 1994 Report to the General Assembly, stated: cooperative enterprises provide the organizational means whereby a significant proportion of humanity is able to take into its own hands the tasks of creating productive employment, overcoming poverty and achieving social integration (Somavia, 2020).
2. **Role in Raising Capital:** Small enterprises have a great difficulty in obtaining capital, due to the poor match between their capital needs and the operating rules of the capital markets. Of all financing options available to SME, including a reluctant financial market and cash strapped government; cooperatives appear to be a most reliable option. Cooperatives, particularly financial cooperatives are response of the market itself to mobilize resources and make same available to SME and other users through appropriate institutional arrangement, thus explaining the recourse of some development agencies to channel funds meant for SMEs through cooperatives (Fischer, 2018).
3. **Role in Provision of Infrastructural Facilities:** Inadequate infrastructure has been a problem to SMEs in Nigeria like in other countries. Cooperatives have often been able to provide some of these facilities by establishing joint production facilities for members with full compliments of tools, electricity, access road etc. (cooperative society as a common workplace). In other words, members have formed the cooperative society primarily as a form of "organized self-employment". Typical examples are collective agricultural cooperatives, small industrial cooperatives and entrepreneurs' cooperatives (Somavia, 2020). A good example of this will be the HUDMCS where traders and businessmen in Anambra State established an international market with all the necessary infrastructural facilities such as electricity, access roads, water supply, security, etc. In some cases, cooperatives had integrated vertically to establish such common workplaces at the secondary cooperative levels.
4. **Role in Small Scale Industrialization:** Cooperatives are also known to have increasingly promoted and supported small production and manufacturing enterprises, such as oil palm mills, maize processing facilities are often established as common work facilities or production cooperatives, in South East Nigeria. The handicraft and other local art ventures are also increasingly receiving the support and assistance of cooperatives in such states like Cross River and Akwa Ibom States. In production cooperatives that are established to promote industrialization members are usually the employees or workers of the cooperative (Somavia, 2020).
5. **Role in Developing Smallholder Agriculture:** Historically, agricultural cooperatives have been a successful and common aspect of rural life in Nigeria. These cooperatives have allowed for economic stability and provided a framework for local investment that is community based. Aside from traditional agricultural and livestock ventures, agricultural activities focusing on livestock, fishing, forestry, and other natural resource-based

activities have also been effectively promoted (Somavia, 2020). The attraction of agricultural cooperative to farmers is largely because of its role in farm inputs supply, marketing and processing and credit disbursements.

Theoretical Framework

Theory of Democracy

The principal objective of this theory is to make co-operative an easy and profitable organization in which their aims and objectives are achieved. The theory provides at least some of the materials required to enable us to make a realistic assessment of decision making in retail co-operatives. An appraisals, however requires more than facts. If we desire to make some judgment about how democratic co-operatives really are, we need first of all a clear conception of the meaning of the term "Democracy". Although there is no agreed definition of democracy, even though a cursory study of the uses of the term by modern writers and politicians shows that there is no agreed meaning. Some equate it with the rule of the majority, others emphasis the importance of protecting the rights of the minority. Some regard it as a system, which maintains certain valued institution, such as freedom of speech and association, while others said a way, which totalitarian democracy. Co-operative democracy could be view as the democratically control in the co-operative set-up, that is, democracy within co-operatives. The concrete elements in a co-operative democracy may of course, be different from those in a state democracy. For example, in a cooperative, the members take the place of the citizens and the Board of Directors take the place of the Government of the state. But these substitutions do not involve a change in the meaning of democracy. And any conclusions, which hold good democracy within the states, will apply equally well to democracy within cooperative societies.

Empirical Review

Fasesin, Babalola and Togun (2021) examined the extent to which cooperative societies empower SMEs financially in Oyo State, Nigeria. A convenience sampling technique was used to select one hundred and sixteen (116) SME operators that are members of cooperatives societies in the selected three cities (Ibadan, Oyo Town, and Ogbomoso) from Oyo State. Data were collected via open and closed questionnaires. Data analysis was performed with the aid of frequencies, percentages, Bar chart, Pie chart, Histogram, and Pearson chi-square. The study revealed that there are a positive and significant relationship between cooperative societies and financial inclusion of SMEs. The study also established that cooperative societies benefit their members by having access to loans without string conditions as applicable in conventional banks. Subsequently, it was recommended that cooperative societies should encourage members to have quick accessibility to loans and they should be faithful to repay their overdue loans. Also, the government should provide viable means of assisting cooperative societies to improve their management activities.

Adegoke, Ajayi and Ajayi (2021) investigated the impact of cooperative society in improving small and medium scale enterprise in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The empirical investigation made use of Descriptive and Linear Regression Analysis. The study employed Small and Medium Enterprise (SME's) as Dependent variable, and Loan extension, Financial Regulation and Cooperative Society as Independent Variables. The finding revealed that there is a positive relationship between loan extension, Cooperative Society, and the growth of SMEs, but a negative relation between Financial Regulation and the SMEs. The study recommended that the government should relax its financial regulations against the SMEs in terms of having access to loans at a less stringent condition in order to boost the enterprise.

Olalekan, Timothy, Ranti and Abayomi (2021) critically examined the activities of cooperative societies in Osun state in furthering SMEs advancement. The study adopted qualitative research method through in-depth exploratory design to explain 'what' and 'how'

rather than mere prediction. A comparative multiple case study was used as it closely links empirical observations with existing theories to explore the effect of cooperative societies on enterprise creation and expansion and its impact on the advancement of SMEs in Osun State, Nigeria. Four cooperatives were selected and studied. Findings affirmed the significant role played by cooperative societies in advancing SMEs in Osun State. The study concludes that cooperative societies' intervention in providing micro loans to members for investment purpose in the area of enterprise formation and expansion is encouraging and should be sustained to improve the prosperity of individuals in Osun State. It was recommended that the promoters of cooperative societies in the State and Nigeria must sustain and increase efforts towards advancing SMEs through the provision of financial facilities to members.

Garandi and Hassan (2020) accessed effect of participation in cooperative society on SMES activities of members in Mubi metropolis, Adamawa state, Nigeria. In order to achieve the objectives, this study was guided by three research hypotheses. Structured questionnaire was used to collect data from randomly selected 376 SMEs operators comprises both members and non-members of cooperatives society in Mubi metropolis. The data collected were analysed with simple percentage, frequency table and t-test analysis. The results of analysis established that the members of cooperative that operating SMEs in Mubi metropolis have significant access to finance such as loan facilities than other SMEs operators. Also, those SMEs operators that were members to cooperative society gained significant access to modern tools and raw materials than non-members. However, the SMEs operators in Mubi metropolis were found less effective in accessing market information for positioning their business. The study concluded that being members of cooperative offers positive advantages for the SMEs operators to develop their enterprises. The study recommends among others that others non-members of cooperative that operate SMEs in Mubi should be encouraged to join the cooperative. Also, there should be training of SMEs operators on how to use information technology for the positioning of their business.

Ademu, Elesho, and Nweke (2019) investigate contribution of cooperative societies on the economic development of Nigeria: using a case study of Kogi state. This research engages a primary source of data with the aid of research questionnaires that were administered to seven hundred and fifty respondents in Yagba east local government in the selected research state. The study employed a descriptive style of research analysis with the use of frequencies and percentages. The result established that the small and medium scale enterprises located in the selected research area were encountered by financial difficulties, which makes it impossible for them to finance their capital project. Furthermore, the cooperative societies who are expected to act as financial back up for this small and medium scale are encountered by lack of skilled personnel to pilot the affairs of this cooperative society. This study recommended that both small and medium scale enterprise and cooperative society should be regulated by the federal government agencies.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study made use of descriptive research design because it would enable the researcher to generalize the findings to a larger population. In this survey research, structured questionnaire was designed to gather information relevant to the research. It involves combination of both social survey and the case study approaches.

Population of the Study

Okezie (2015) defined population as a subset of the target population and is also known as the study population. It is from the accessible population that researchers draw their samples. The total population of the study area; all the members of the studied cooperatives in the study area as follows:

Table 1: List of Cooperative Societies

S/N	Names of cooperative societies	Population
1	Aba North Divisional Cooperative Council Ltd	91
2	Abia State Cooperation Federation Ltd	104
3	All Farmers Association of Nigeria	95
4	Amhuno (Aba) FINCS Ltd	67
5	All Abia State oil palm developer's cooperative society limited	76
6	Eyeh Dike Multi-Purpose Cooperative Society	112
Total		545

Source: Field Survey, 2024

However, the population of the study consists of 545 cooperative members in Aba, Abia State which is subject to systematic random sampling.

Sample Size Determination

The appropriate sample size of the study was determined using Taro Yamane (1967) formula. Therefore, the sample size of the study comprised 231 cooperative members in Aba, Abia State.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection for this study was structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was structured with both open-ended and close-ended questions. In designing the questionnaire, the researcher used 5point likert questions such as Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Strongly disagree (SD) and Undecided (UN). In addition, the researcher also made use of oral interview to collect data from respondents. The primary data were collected through a well-structured questionnaire to obtain all the vital information needed to carry-out the work effectively. The questionnaire was divided into three parts, sections A, B and C. Section A solicited for bio data of respondents and other relevant information. Section B dealt with statements on economic impact of cooperative societies. Section C dealt with statements on small business development in Aba.

Method of Data Collection

Primary data were used for the study. Primary data is the type of data collected solely for the purpose of a study. It is a survey research data and means of gathering information that describes the nature of extent of a specified set of data ranging from physical counts and frequencies to attitude and opinions. To this, both open and close ended questionnaire were carefully preparing and administered to all selected respondents to complete those question contain in the questionnaire. The secondary information was obtained from published journals, textbooks and magazine.

Data Analysis Techniques

The socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents and the objectives were analysed using simple descriptive statistics such as means, frequency distribution, and percentage. Hypotheses were tested with simple linear regression model. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 23) was used as the tool for analysing the primary data obtained.

DATA ANALYSES AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS**Data Presentation*****Effect of Access to Financial Security for the Members on Small Scale Business Development in Aba*****Table 2: Effect of Access to Financial Security for the Members on Small Scale Business Development in Aba**

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	UN	Total	\bar{x}
1. Access to credits(loans) obtained from the cooperative inspires development of my business	106 52.5%	55 27.2%	7 3.5%	14 6.9%	20 9.9%	202 100	4.05
2. Access to cheap and quality inputs (venture capital) enhanced development of my business	145 71.8%	21 10.4%	14 6.9%	12 5.9%	10 5.0%	202 100	4.38
3. Provision of grant to members in distress helps in business sustainability	122 60.4%	27 13.4%	22 10.9	15 7.4%	16 7.9%	202 100	4.10

*Source: Field Survey, 2026**mean > 3.0 accepted, mean < 3.0 rejected*

The effect of access to financial security for the members on small scale business development in Aba was examined in Table 2. From the result, 71.8% of the respondents strongly agreed that, access to cheap and quality inputs (venture capital) enhanced development of their business. This was followed by 60.4% of the respondents strongly agreed that, provision of grant to members in distress helps in business sustainability. More so, 52.5% of the respondents strongly agreed that credits (loans) obtained from the cooperative inspires development of their business. However, it's only, 9.9% of the respondents that were uncertain that credits (loans) obtained from the cooperative inspires development of my business. The precision through the mean value decision rule that, a mean value > 3.0 was accepted while a mean < 3.0 was rejected. From the descriptive questions, the three questions (items) had a mean value of 4.05, 4.38 and 4.10, respectively. In effect, the researcher concluded that access to financial security for the members has a strong effect on small scale business development in Aba.

Table 3: Effect of Cooperative Saving Habit on Small Scale Business Development in Aba

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	UN	Total	\bar{x}
1. Weekly saving structure by cooperative members assist in business development	87 43.1%	42 20.8%	22 10.9%	25 12.4%	26 12.9%	202 100	3.68
2. Mandatory withholding of members contributions helps in small business growth	75 37.1%	69 34.2%	26 12.9%	14 6.9%	18 8.9%	202 100	3.83
3. Cooperative assistance in encouraging saving habit increases business development	104 51.5%	46 22.8%	17 8.4%	16 7.9%	19 9.4%	202 100	3.99

*Source: Field Survey, 2026**mean > 3.0 accepted, mean < 3.0 rejected*

The effect of cooperative saving habit on small scale business development in Aba was examined in Table 3. From the result, 51.5% of the respondents strongly agreed that, cooperative assistance in encouraging saving habit increases business development; followed by 43.1% of the respondents strongly agreed that, weekly saving structure by cooperative members assist in business development. More so, 37.1% of the respondents strongly agreed that mandatory withholding of members contributions helps in small business growth. However, 12.9% of the respondents disagreed that, mandatory withholding of members contributions helps in small business growth. The precision through the mean value decision rule that, a mean value > 3.0 was accepted while a mean < 3.0 was rejected. From the

descriptive questions, the three questions (items) had a mean value of 3.68, 3.83 and 3.99; all above 3.0, in effect, the researcher concluded that cooperative saving habit contributes strongly to the small scale business development in Aba.

Table 4: Effect of Storage Facility Provision on Small Scale Business Development in Aba

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	UN	Total	\bar{x}
1. Cooperative society assist in provision of storage facility	57 28.2%	40 19.8%	35 17.3%	39 19.3%	31 15.4	202 100	3.26
2. Membership to cooperative inspires on stunning and grading goods for future use	23 11.4%	18 8.9%	62 30.7%	65 32.2%	34 16.8	202 100	2.65
3. Cooperative assist in providing warehouse for small business owners	29 14.4%	38 18.8%	36 17.8%	60 29.7%	39 19.3	202 100	2.79

Source: Field Survey, 2026

mean > 3.0 accepted, mean < 3.0 rejected

The effect of storage facility provision on small scale business development in Aba was examined in Table 4. The result revealed that, majority of the respondents 19.8% agreed that, cooperative society assist in provision of storage facility. However, 32.2% of the respondents who strongly disagreed that, membership to cooperative inspires on stunning and grading goods for future use. More so, 29.7% strongly disagreed that cooperative assist in providing warehouse for small business owners. The precision through the mean value decision rule that, a mean value > 3.0 was accepted while a mean < 3.0 was rejected. As shown in the result, one descriptive question (items) had a mean value above 3.0 (3.26) while two statements had a mean value below 3.0 (2.65 and 2.79), in effect, the research concluded there is no significant effect storage facility provision and small-scale business development in Aba.

Table 5: Effect of Provision of Marketing Agencies of Products on Small Scale Business Development in Aba

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	UN	Total	\bar{x}
1. The cooperative assist members in providing market information as at when due	88 43.6%	33 16.3%	32 15.8%	24 11.9	25 12.4	202 100	3.66
2. Pricing strategy adopted by the cooperative is favorable and profitable to members	94 45.5%	49 24.3%	26 12.9%	20 9.9%	13 6.4%	202 100	3.94
3. Cooperative assist in promotion and sales of finished products for their members	71 35.1%	46 22.8%	25 12.4%	33 16.3	27 13.4	202 100	3.50

Source: Field Survey, 2026

mean > 3.0 accepted, mean < 3.0 rejected

The effect of provision of marketing agencies of products on small scale business development in Aba was examined in Table 4.4. The result revealed that majority of the respondents 45.5% strongly agreed that the pricing strategy adopted by the cooperative is favorable and profitable to members. Followed by 43.6% of the respondents who strongly agreed that the cooperative assist members in providing market information as at when due. More so, 35.1% who agreed that cooperative assist in promotion and sales of finished products for their members. However, 16.3% strongly disagreed that cooperative assist in promotion and sales of finished products for their members. The precision through the mean value decision rule that, a mean value > 3.0 was accepted while a mean < 3.0 was rejected. As shown in the result, three descriptive questions (items) had a mean value above 3.0, in effect, the research concluded there is a significant effect of provision of marketing agencies of products and small scale business development in Aba.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

The study examined economic impact of cooperative societies on small scale business development in Aba, Abia State, Nigeria. Economic impact of cooperative societies was proxied by access to financial security for the members, cooperative saving habit, storage facility provision and marketing agencies of products, while small scale business development in Aba was maintained as dependent variable. A descriptive research design was used for the study. The population of the study consisted of 545 members of the studied cooperative societies operating small businesses. The sample of the study 202 was drawn through Taro Yamane formula and simple random sampling technique was used. Questionnaire was the major instrument for data collection. Simple linear regression analysis hypotheses were used to test hypotheses 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively. The result of the findings indicated that, there is significant effect of access to financial security by the members on small scale business development in Aba, Abia State. Also, there is significant effect of cooperative saving habit on small scale business development in Aba. There is significant effect of marketing agencies of products on small scale business development in Aba, Nigeria. However, there is no significant effect of storage facility provision on small scale business development in Aba, Abia State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made for;

1. Since, there is significant effect of access to financial security by the members on small scale business development, cooperative societies should encourage members to have quick accessibility to loans and they should be faithful to repay their overdue loans. Also, the government should provide viable means of assisting cooperative societies to improve their management activities.
2. Also, there is significant effect of cooperative saving habit on small scale business development in Aba, thus the promoters of cooperative societies in the Aba and Nigeria must sustain and increase efforts towards advancing SMEs through the provision of daily saving of financial outcome to members.
3. The study showed that there is no significant effect of storage facility provision on small scale business development in Aba, Abia State. In effect, there is need for government, NGOs and international development agencies to increase the tempo of their storage facilities and support-service to the activities of marketing cooperative societies in view of their importance in Nigeria.
4. The result further revealed that there is significant effect of marketing agencies of products on small scale business development in Aba. The study advocates for increased support to establishment fish marketing cooperatives as they have great potential to facilitate sales of products and easy buying of inputs to empower their members socially and economically.

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